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Research Article

ARRHYTHMIA RISK DURING PREGNANCIES IN LATTER AGE AMONG FEMALES IN JINNAH HOSPITAL LAHORE

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Abstract:

Objective: The deaths of various cardiovascular diseases occur in pregnancies of advance age & third most common reason of this high mortality rate is arrhythmia. The aim of this research work is to determine whether arrhythmia risk rises in females with pregnancy in latter age.

Methodology: Total two hundred and eighty females with pregnancy of whom ninety eight females were available with advance age and one hundred eighty two females under thirty five year of age were the part of this research work. The evaluation of the danger of presence of arrhythmia carried out with the assessment of duration of electrocardiographic P wave duration, interval of QT, interval of T peak to end & ratio of Tp-e/QT.

Results: Though we found no disparities in interval of Tp-e & ratio of Tp-e/QTc between the participants of both groups, highest QTc, lowest QTc, & dispersion values of QTc were very high among the females having pregnancy in advance age as compared to pregnant females of healthy control group. Additionally, P dispersion was higher in pregnant females in elder age. In association examination, the high QTc dispersion & increased P were available with correlation with the age of pregnant female. Regression analysis displayed that the dispersion of QTc was also have association with the age of pregnant female. **Conclusion:** Repolarization features rise in the pregnancy of advance ages though they are available in a normal span, which are necessary to be under investigation of whether this condition is a cause of any disease.

Key Words: Arrhythmia, methodology, pregnancy, electrocardiogram, regression, interval.

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INTRODUCTION:

In the duration of last twenty years, the reproductive attitude of females have changed because of improvement in the social and economic condition, high level of education and hardships linked with gaining jobs, so, females planned pregnancies at latter age of their life [1]. In the country of Canada, the amount of live births to females thirty to thirty nine year of age has increases from 23.60% in the year 1982 to 45.90% in the year of 2005 [2]. But, the elder age of female has displayed an association with low fertility & high dangers of stillbirths, live birth before term, low weight at the time of birth & adverse outcome of pregnancy [3-5]. Various research works have discovered that females with pregnancy over thirty five year of age had adverse outcome of pregnancy and normally considered as cutoff age [1-5]. In one research work, interrogating in the duration of pregnancy up until complete one year after delivery, 22.20% maternal mortalities were present due to cardiovascular complications & females of these diseases were of high age and met their death in after delivery duration. The very common reason was the cardiomyopathy whereas arrhythmic mortalities were the 3rd most frequent reason [6].

Advance age of female is responsible for a rise in the morbidity as well as mortality in the period of pregnancy, in obstetric complications and high risk of death of infant miscarriage & stillbirth, no research work has assessed the danger of arrhythmia, which is one of the main causes of cardiovascular problems responsible for the maternal mortality.

METHODOLOGY:

The ethical committee of Jinnah Hospital, Lahore gave the approval of this transverse research work. Pregnant females with advance age of more than thirty five year of age and healthy controls with less than thirty five year of age in the same trimester were the part of this research work. These females got admission in this very hospital in the obstetric department. There were total two hundred and eighty females with pregnancy in which ninety eight females were present with

advance age & one hundred and eighty two females were less than thirty five year of age. Females suffering from any other serious complication or chronic disease were not the part of this research work.

A twelve lead electrocardiograph recorded for every pregnant female only one time in the final trimester in spine position. We acquired the recordings at paper speed of fifty mm/s, with standardization of one mV/cm. We enhanced our preciseness with the utilization of the calipers & magnifying lenses. Initiation of P wave was very 1st atrial deflection from the line of isoelectric & offset was retrieval to the value of baseline. The measurement of highest & lowest duration of P wave carried out & their disparities were the P dispersion. Measurement of interval of QT carried out from the start of QRS complex to termination of T wave & adjusted for rate of heart rate utilizing the Bazett formula: $cQT = QT \sqrt{(R-R \text{ interval})}$. The interval of Tpe was the duration between peak & termination of T wave. The calculations of interval of Tp-e carried out utilizing precordial leads & ratio Tp-e / QTc measured from all these calculations.

SPSS V. 21 was in use for the statistical analysis of the gathered information. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov method was in use for the testing of normality of distribution of patients. Average & SD values were in use for the presentation of the numerical variables. T test was in use for the comparison of various variables of two groups. Chi square test was in use for the Categorical feature. For the indication of the correlation of advance maternal age with the duration of QTc, interval of Tp-e & ratio of Tp-e/QTc Pearson Rank test was in use. Regression analysis carried out for the determination of the predictors of dispersion of QTc.

RESULTS:

All the females with pregnancy were nulliparous & they were in their third trimester of pregnancy duration. Obstetric as well as demographic traits of groups are available in Table-1.

Table-I: Characteristics of the study population.

Characteristics	Group-1 (>35 years)		Group-2 (<35 years)		P-value
	Mean	± SD	Mean	± SD	
Maternal age, years	38.50	2.57	23.50	4.16	<0.0010
Gestational week	34.70	3.50	33.40	3.40	0.0080
BMI, kg/m ²	30.40	4.90	28.20	4.30	<0.0010
Heart rate, bpm	90.70	14.80	89.90	15.50	0.6800
Systolic BP, mmHg	117.40	9.60	112.40	10.20	<0.0010
Diastolic BP, mmHg	70.80	8.60	64.60	8.60	<0.0010

The females of the Group-1 were of advance age. Females were in their advance week of gestation and BMI was naturally high among the females of Group-1. Their BP was in routine values. The characteristics of laboratory findings of pregnant females with advance age & healthy controls at the time of admission are present in Table-2.

Table-II: Laboratory tests results of the study population at assessment.

Laboratory Results	Group-1 (>35 years)		Group-2 (<35 years)		P-value
	Mean	± SD	Mean	± SD	
Hemoglobin (g/dl)	11.80	1.30	11.80	1.20	0.8400
Platelet (x103) -	242.60	59.40	229.10	65.00	0.0800
/pLWBC	11508.00	2422.00	12036.00	2135.00	0.1000
BUN (mg/dl)	16.30	3.90	16.60	4.70	0.5300
Creatinine (mg/dl)	0.48	0.08	0.46	0.07	0.0600
Sodium (mEq/L)	137.40	1.90	137.80	1.80	0.4200
Potassium (mEq/L)	4.10	0.30	4.10	0.20	0.9300

Though we found no disparity in the interval of Tp-e & ratio of Tp-e/QTc between the participants of both groups, highest QTc, lowest QTc & dispersion values of QTc were expressively greater in the patients group in comparison with the group of healthy controls Table-3.

Table-III: The electrocardiographic findings of the study population.

Findings	Group-1 (>35 years)		Group-2 (<35 years)		P-value
	Mean	± SD	Mean	± SD	
Maximum QTc	403.70	27.80	393.30	14.60	< 0.001
Minimum QTc	381.80	23.70	373.80	13.20	0.0020
QTc dispersion (ms)	21.80	8.70	19.50	7.20	0.0100
Tp-e interval (ms)	76.30	13.00	74.20	13.00	0.1900
Tp-e/QTc ratio	0.18	0.03	0.18	0.03	0.8600
P dispersion (ms)	19.50	7.50	17.80	7.20	0.0500

Additionally, P dispersion was higher in the females with pregnancy of high age. In the analysis of bivariate correlation, enhanced QTc dispersion & P was available with association with the age of pregnant female (Table-4).

Table-IV: Correlation analysis between electrocardiographic findings and clinical characteristics in pregnant.

	Maternal age	BMI
Maximum QTc	r: 0.2410	r: 0.115
	p:<0.0010	p:0.060
Minimum QTc	r:0 .1920	r: 0.1130
	p:0.0010	p:0.060
QTc dispersion	r: 0.199	r:0.0140
	p:0.001	p:0.060
Mean QTc	r: 0.2250	r:0.1110
	p:<0.0010	p:0.070
Tp-e interval	r: 0.1230	r:-0.0720
	p:0.080	p:0.230
Tp-e/QTc ratio	r: 0.0560	r: -0.1100
	p:0.330	p:0.070
P dispersion	r: 0.1320	r: 0.080
	p: 0.020	p:0.160

Regression analysis displayed that dispersion of QTc was available with an association with the age of pregnant female (Table-5).

Table-V: Results of multivariable analysis of independent predictors of QTc dispersion.

Parameters	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	P-value
Maternal age	0.1790	0.1830	0.0030
BMI	12.8	0.0070	0.2100

DISCUSSION:

The major outcomes of this research work are, the atrial & ventricular repolarization features parameters were greater in the females with pregnancy and of high age in comparison with the young females with pregnancy. Additionally, determination carried out about the repolarization features of atrial & ventricular enhanced with the increase of maternal age, whereas only the age of mother was prognostic of the dispersion of QTc. Because of social & economic advancement & long duration of education, females have initiated of getting pregnancy in the advance age of their lives. So, the cardiovascular complications as gynecological issue has increased.

Briller interrogated in his research work that particular reason maternal mortality where greater than 20.0% of maternal mortality found with relation to cardiovascular problems like arrhythmia and greater than 25.0% Of these mortalities were possibly avoidable [6]. One research work showed that the rate of arrhythmias enhanced largely because of the activity of ventricular ectopic in the young normal pregnancies, especially in those who had complaints of palpitation [7]. The hormones of reproduction play a vital part in initiation & development of arrhythmia like supra-ventricular tachycardia & obtained syndrome of long QT [8, 9].

Electrocardiogram is very frequent tool for the prediction of presence of arrhythmia in medical practice. Currently established markers like interval of Tp-e & ratio of Tp-e / QTc anticipated as identifiers for prediction of incidence of cardiac arrhythmia & suggested as substitutes for stratification of risk of immediate cardiac death in females with different clinical condition [10-12]. In one research work, assessing the danger of this complication in the group of preeclampsia (PE), the highest QT, dispersion of QTc, interval of Tp-e & values of Tp-e/QTc were available as very high in the group of PE in comparison with the healthy controls [13]. The findings also showed that although these values increased in the affected females but these values were still present in normal range [14]. Currently, Braschi showed the rise in the markers of the ventricular repolarization with enhance age [15].

CONCLUSION:

The findings of this research work conclude that repolarization features were high in the pregnancies of advance age even these values were in routine range which will be the matter of explanation in further studies those will investigate whether is a state of disease. If that was a pathological condition, the establishment of the scoring of risk of arrhythmia is

necessary to decrease the morbidity as well as mortality in pregnant females of advance stage and in their final trimester.

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